

Evaluation of Teacher-centered and Learner-centered methods for Instructional Delivery of Psychological courses in Rivers State Universities

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Abstract

The study examined the evaluation of teacher-centered and learner-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities. Two objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study was carried out in Rivers State. This study adopted an evaluation research design. The population of the study consisted of 40 psychology lecturers in Rivers state university, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education and University of Port-Harcourt. Census was used to engage all the population in the study due to small population size. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "Evaluation of Teacher-centred and Learner-centered Methods for Instructional Delivery of Psychological Courses". The instrument was face and content validated by two experts in measurement and evaluation. The reliability of the study was established using Kuder Richardson-20. The reliability coefficient obtained was 0.73. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and one way analysis of variance for testing hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Items with mean responses of equal to or greater than 2.50 were rated effective while mean responses less than 2.50 were rated ineffective. The study found that learner centred approach according to the study, was found to be effective in sharing classroom responsibilities and participation in learning activities, encouraging learners' initiatives, creates balance between teachers' need and learners' need, aids construction of shared understanding and creates collaborative learning environment where knowledge is constructed by both teacher and learner. the study recommended that Psychology lecturers should adopt areas of effectiveness in teacher-centred teaching method, so as to complement their various teaching methods used in conveying instructions to their learners.

Keywords: Evaluation, Teacher-Centred, Learner-Centred, Instructional Delivery

INTRODUCTION

The aim of teaching psychology courses in tertiary institution is to enable students develop the ability to understand people, provide counselling service and therapy for people in distress. Psychology course comprises of diverse topics that enables learners to gain comprehension of human behaviour such as anxiety in children, the interpretation of dreams, the effects of caffeine on thinking, how people from different cultures react differently in negotiation, and the factors that lead people to engage in terrorism alcohol and drug addiction, memory, emotion, hypnosis, love, what makes people aggressive or helpful, and the psychologies of politics, prejudice, culture, and religion. Basically, the teaching of psychology courses helps to develop intuition in learners and to understand the principles of human behaviour.

Psychology is defined as "the scientific study of behaviour and mental processes" (Coon & Mitterer, 2010). Although it comprises many sub-disciplines and theoretical perspectives that vary in methods, scope and area of focus, the modern practice of psychology, in both academic and applied settings, employs scientific

rigor in the examination of human behaviour. There are many sub-disciplines in the field of psychology, just to mention few are behavioural psychology, abnormal psychology, developmental psychology, counselling psychology among others. Behavioral psychology, or behaviorism, is a theory suggesting that environment shapes human behavior. In a most basic sense, behavioral psychology is the study and analysis of observable behavior. This field of psychology influenced thought heavily throughout the middle of the 20th century. It is still used by mental health professionals today, as its concepts and theories remain relevant in fields like psychotherapy and education. Behavioral psychology is concerned with the conditions involved in development, maintenance, control, and elimination of the behavior of individuals and other organisms (Bufford, 1999). It focuses on understanding and modifying individuals' thoughts, feelings, and behaviors.

According to Bridley and Daffin (2022), abnormal Psychology refers to the scientific study of abnormal behaviour, with the intent to be able to predict reliably,

explain, diagnose, identify the causes of, and treat maladaptive behaviour. They further defined abnormal behavior as the combination of personal distress, psychological dysfunction, deviance from social norms, dangerousness to self and others, and costliness to society. While developmental psychology focuses on human growth and changes across the lifespan, including physical, cognitive, social, intellectual, perceptual, personality and emotional growth. It is concerned with human growth and development over the lifespan, including physical, cognitive, social, intellectual, perceptual, personality and emotional growth. Counselling psychology is also another one of the major sub-disciplines of psychology which is concerned with uses a broad range of culturally informed and culturally sensitive practices to help people improve their well-being, prevent and alleviate distress and maladjustment, resolve crises, and increase their ability to function better in their lives. It focuses specifically but not exclusively on normative life-span development, with a particular emphasis on prevention and education as well as amelioration, addressing individuals as well as the systems or contexts in which they function (American Psychology Association, 2008).

There are variety of teaching methods that are proven to be effective in teaching and learning process. Psychology affects every facet of our lives. A human being usually exhibits moods of joy and anger, have different learning ability, and interact differently. When certain situations occur, there is eagerness in finding the circumstances that are surrounding these actions and logical make judgments (Alao & Adeniyi, 2008). This makes psychology courses to be unique to not only developing the knowledge of learners but also help them use the knowledge make theoretical conclusion about human and animal behaviour.

Many teachers strive to implement a blend of teacher-centered and student-centered styles sometimes within the same classroom, based on their own instincts, research and experience. According to Hill (2002), teacher-centred approaches are more traditional in nature, focusing on the teacher as instructor. They are sometimes referred to as direct instruction, deductive teaching or expository teaching, and are typified by the lecture type presentation. In these methods of teaching, the teacher controls what is to be taught and how students are presented with the information that they are

to learn. Teacher-centered instructional methods are also known as traditional instructional methods, where teachers are at the center of classroom activities, including explanations and discussions (Ahmad & Aziz, 2009). In teacher-centered classrooms, control is of primary importance and “authority is transmitted hierarchically” (Dollard & Christensen in Garret, 2008), meaning the teacher exerts control over the students. Critics of teacher-centeredness argue that in these classrooms, compliance is valued over initiative and passive learners’ over-active learners (Freiberg, 1999). To help teachers maintain control over students, instructional methods that promote a focus on the teacher are frequently used, such as lectures, guided discussions, demonstration and “cookbook” labs (Edwards, 2004).

Educators who use teacher-centered approaches are generally reluctant to use esoteric forms of instruction, and many effective teachers have not found success using student-centered teaching approaches. There is some evidence that, despite the heavy emphasis placed on student-centered techniques, many social studies teachers prefer using teacher-centered instruction in the classroom (Shug, n.d). Teacher centered method is behaviourist in nature. Teacher-directed learning that follow the instructive approach which involves careful and meticulous planning of the curriculum and purposeful instructional procedure employed by teacher (Ubulom & Ogwunte, 2017). McDowell (2001) noted that instructional method that encourages memorization and reproduction are short knowledge that can be used to solve problems in new situations. Tella, Indoshi & Othuon (2010) noted that teacher centered methods often result to students not enjoying lessons and missing the benefits of intellectual discovery. The use of teacher-centred method often results in the production of learners who are only have knowledge of theories but lack application abilities.

Contrarily, students- centered approach is a teaching method that focuses on students and not teacher. The student-centered approach to education also has relevance for teachers who choose to develop a deeper understanding of the art and science of education by pursuing a master’s degree (Lathan, 2022). For example, in contrast to the more teacher-centered approach that is common to on-campus programs, online master’s degree programs tend to place more emphasis on interacting with one’s fellow degree

candidates across the country through the learning portals that are an essential component of the online academic experience. According to Garret (2008) as against the traditional instruction, this student-centered approach focuses on meaning making, inquiry and authentic activity. The instructional goal in student-centered classrooms, based on constructivist principles of learning, is to create a learning environment where knowledge is constructed by the teacher and students rather than transmitted directly by the teacher. Brophy (2006) explains that in these classrooms students are expected to strive to make sense of what they are learning by relating it to prior knowledge and by discussing it with others. The class acts as “a learning community that constructs shared understanding” (Brophy, 1999). To complement this shift in instructional approach, some school reformers and researchers propose a shift in classroom management approach. Student centred approaches (sometimes referred to as discovery learning, inductive learning, or inquiry learning) place a much stronger emphasis on the learner’s role in the learning process. When you are using student- centred approaches to teaching, you still set the learning agenda but you have much less direct control over what and how students learn (Hill, 2002) Theoretically, it makes sense to assume that teachers would actively try to align their instructional and administrative approaches, notwithstanding educators' worries about a potential mismatch between management and instruction (Garret, 2008). Teachers that are committed to student-centered instruction are likely to base their judgments on a fundamental understanding of how students learn and what they require from their learning environment. For instance, it seems reasonable to anticipate that such teachers will select classroom management techniques like peer mediation and conflict resolution that foster the same skills if they believe that children need to be active participants in the learning process, engage in critical thinking, and participate in the problem-solving process.

According Felders (N.D) The traditional teacher-centered approach to instruction has repeatedly been shown to be inferior to learner-centered methods. According to him, this conclusion holds true regardless of whether the assessed outcome is short-term mastery, long-term retention, or depth of understanding of course material, acquisition of critical thinking or creative

problem-solving skills, development of positive attitudes toward the subject being taught, or degree of knowledge and skill self-confidence. Due to the objective of psychology courses, there is need to evaluate teacher-centred and learner-centered teaching method for instructional delivery of psychology courses in Rivers State Universities.

Statement of Problem

Based on observations, the researcher has noticed that majority of psychology students rarely take up career in the discipline. This may be due to their inability to; provide understanding to human complexities, understand people, provide counselling service and therapy for people in distress. Ubulom and Ogwunte (2017) have attributed students’ under performance and skill incompetency to absence of effective teaching method. In line with Ubulom and Ogwunte, the researcher observed that students who are taught psychology are only efficient in rote memorization of theories and concepts in psychology and not in the application of these theories to produce needed result. It is therefore expedient to evaluate the evaluate teacher-centred and learner-centered teaching method for instructional delivery of psychology courses in Rivers State Universities

Purpose of the study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate teacher-centered and learner-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in some Nigerian Universities. Specifically, the study sought to

1. determine the effectiveness of context, input, process and product of teacher-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities
2. Determine the effectiveness of context, input, process and product of learner-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. How effective is the context, input, process and product of teacher-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities?
2. How effective is the context, input, process and product of learner-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female psychology lecturers on the effectiveness of context, input, process, and product of teacher-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female psychology lecturers on the effectiveness of the context, input, process and product of learner-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities

METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Rivers State. This study adopted an evaluation research design. This design was used because the study tends to provide value judgment on the teacher-centred and learner-centred methods of instructional delivery of psychological courses. The study adopted an CIPP (Context, Input, Process and Product) evaluation model. The evaluation model was developed by Stufflebeam in 1971 which consisted of four (4) interrelated domains of evaluation, namely: C = Context, I = Input, P = Process and P = Product. The population of the study consisted of 40 psychology

lecturers in Rivers State University-5, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education-14 and University of Port-Harcourt-21. Census was used to engage all the population in the study due to small population size. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled “Evaluation of Teacher-Centred and Learner-Centered Methods for Instructional Delivery of Psychological Courses (ETLMIDPC)”. The instrument used for data collection was designed in in a four-point rating scale of Very Effective (VE-4), Effective (E-3), Ineffective (D-2), Very ineffective (SD-1). The instrument was face and content validated by two experts in measurement and evaluation. The reliability of the study was established using Kuder Richardson-20. The reliability coefficient obtained was 0.73. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for testing hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Items with mean responses of equal to or greater than 2.50 were rated effective while mean responses less than 2.50 were rated ineffective.

RESULT

Research Question 1: How effective is the context, input, process and product of teacher-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities?

Table 1: Mean Responses of Lecturers on How Effective the Context, Input, Process and Product of Teacher-Centered Methods for Instructional Delivery of Psychological Courses

SN	Items	RSU=5		R m	IAUE=14		Rm	UNIPOINT=21		
		Mean	S.D.		Mean	S.D.		Mean	S.D.	Rm
1	Teachers’ sole leadership/control of classroom management	3.02	0.76	E	3.32	0.76	E	3.31	0.76	E
2	Instructional methods promote focus on the teacher alone	2.21	1.21	IE	2.28	1.21	IE	2.39	1.21	IE
3	Limits students’ activities in disrupting attention to the teacher	3.07	0.81	E	3.14	0.81	E	3.26	0.81	E
4	Encourage students’ compliance to classroom rules over initiative	3.06	0.83	E	3.09	0.83	E	3.12	0.83	E
5	Opportunities for learners’ contribution	2.01	1.08	IE	2.31	1.08	IE	2.12	1.08	IE
6	Teachers exerts of discipline on students in the classroom	3.02	0.72	E	2.89	0.72	E	3.07	0.72	E
7	Oversight classroom management	3.81	0.35	E	3.42	0.38	E	3.22	0.38	E
8	Extrinsic rewards system	3.19	0.67	E	3.25	0.62	E	3.10	0.62	E
9	Encourages passive learners	3.20	0.82	E	3.13	0.49	E	3.45	0.49	E
10	Utilization of instructional materials	2.33	1.02	IE	2.48	1.10	IE	2.03	1.10	IE
11	Instructions is delivered confidently	3.52	0.61	E	3.42	0.61	E	2.87	0.61	E

	and comfortably by the teacher									
12	Creates opportunity for students' and teacher to collaborate	1.87	0.42	IE	2.04	1.12	IE	2.10	1.12	IE
13	Students develop communication and crucial thinking	2.10	1.03	IE	2.32	1.03	IE	2.29	1.03	IE
Grand Mean & S.D		2.80	0.79		2.85	0.83		2.79	0.83	

Field Survey, 2022

Table 1 presents the mean responses of lecturers on how effective the context, input, process and product of teacher-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses. Based on the criterion mean of 2.50, the study indicated that teacher-centred is effective in teachers' sole leadership/control of classroom management (3.02, 3.32 & 3.31), limits students' activities in disrupting attention to the teacher (3.07, 3.14 & 3.26), encourage students' compliance to classroom rules over initiative (3.06, 3.09 & 3.12), teachers' exerts of discipline on students in the classroom (3.02, 2.89 & 3.07), oversight classroom management (3.81, 3.42 & 3.22), extrinsic rewards system (3.19, 3.25 & 3.10), encourages passive learners (3.20, 3.13 & 3.45), and instructions is delivered

confidently and comfortably by the teacher (3.52, 3.42 & 2.87). The study also revealed that teacher-centred teaching method is ineffective for instructional delivery in the following; instructional methods promote focus on the teacher alone (2.21, 2.28 & 2.39), opportunities for learners' contribution (2.01, 2.31 & 2.12), utilization of instructional materials (2.33, 2.48 & 2.03), creates opportunity for students' and teacher to collaborate (1.87, 2.04 & 2.10) and students develop communication and crucial thinking (2.10, 2.32 & 2.29)

Research Questions 2: How effective is the context, input, process and product of learner-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities?

Table 2: Mean Responses of Lecturers on How Effective the Context, Input, Process and Product of Learner-Centered Methods for Instructional Delivery of Psychological Courses

S/N	Items	RSU=5			IAUE=14			UNIPORT=21		
		Mean	S.D	Rm	Mean	S.D	Rm	Mean	S.D	Rm
1	Shared leadership of teachers and students	2.88	1.02	E	2.08	1.10	E	3.01	0.96	E
2	Guiding students to understanding	3.58	0.64	E	3.25	0.85	E	2.98	1.05	E
3	Sharing classroom responsibilities and participation in learning activities	3.42	0.53	E	3.37	0.62	E	3.52	0.67	E
4	Facilitation of classroom management	2.10	1.14	IE	2.39	1.03	IE	2.10	1.13	IE
5	Creates collaborative learning environment where knowledge is constructed by both teacher and learner	3.47	0.62	E	3.41	0.66	E	3.22	0.78	E
6	Students are expected to strive to make sense of what they are learning	3.23	0.71	E	3.11	0.68	E	3.29	0.69	E
7	Aids construction of shared understanding	3.02	0.72	E	3.45	0.63	E	3.42	0.59	E
8	Creates balance between teachers' need and learners' need	3.29	0.62	E	3.34	0.60	E	3.28	0.63	E
9	Intrinsic reward system	3.34	0.69	E	3.39	0.57	E	3.42	0.68	E
10	Leads to learning by discovery and guidance	3.02	0.65	E	3.06	0.81	E	3.04	0.87	E
11	Encouraging learners' initiatives	3.42	0.71	E	3.64	0.48	E	3.25	0.54	E
12	Utilization of instructional materials	3.55	0.66	E	3.28	0.66	E	3.52	0.50	E
13	Students' build both collaboration and communication skill	3.29	0.74	E	3.22	0.65	E	3.46	0.59	E

14	Students' independent working and interaction	3.13	0.83	E	3.10	0.61	E	3.11	0.61	E
15	Controlled classroom	2.21	1.04	IE	2.17	1.02	IE	2.07	1.12	IE
Grand Mean & S.D		3.13	0.75		3.08	0.73		3.11	0.76	

Field Survey, 2022; E- Effective, IE- Ineffective

Table 2 present the mean responses of lecturers on how effective the context, input, process and product of learner-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses. Based on the criterion mean of 2.50, the study indicated that learner-centred is effective in shared leadership of teachers and students (2.88, 2.08 & 3.01), guiding students to understanding (3.58, 3.25 & 2.98), sharing classroom responsibilities and participation in learning activities (3.42, 3.37 & 3.52), creates collaborative learning environment where knowledge is constructed by both teacher and learner (3.47, 3.41 & 3.22), students are expected to strive to make sense of what they are learning (3.23, 3.11 & 3.29), aids construction of shared understanding (3.02, 3.45 & 3.42), creates balance between teachers' need and learners' need (3.29, 3.34 & 3.28), intrinsic reward system (3.34 , 3.39 & 3.42), leads to learning by

discovery and guidance (3.02, 3.06 & 3.04), encouraging learners' initiatives (3.42, 3.64 & 3.25), utilization of instructional materials (3.55, 3.28 & 3.52), students' build both collaboration and communication skill (3.29, 3.22 & 3.46), students' independent working and interaction (3.13, 3.10 & 3.11). However, the finding recorded ineffectiveness in facilitating classroom management (2.10, 2.10 & 2.10) and controlling classroom settings (2.21, 2.17 & 2.07).

Test of hypotheses

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of psychology lecturers in RSU, IAUE and UNIPORT on the effectiveness of context, input, process, and product of teacher-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities

Table 3: One Way ANOVA analysis on effectiveness of context, input, process, and product of teacher-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-cal	F-crit	Sig.	Remark
Between Groups	.315	2	.157	.579	3.23	.566	N.S
Within Groups	10.068	37	.272				
Total	10.382	39					

Research Data Output

Table 3 shows one way ANOVA analysis on effectiveness of context, input, process, and product of teacher-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities. The analysis on showed that the f-cal (0.579) is less than the f-crit (3.23) at 0.05 level of significance, 2 degrees of freedom in the numerator and 37 degrees of freedom in the denominator. Furthermore, p-value obtained was 0.566 which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female psychology

lecturers on the effectiveness of context, input, process, and product of teacher-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities.

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of psychology lecturers in RSU, IAUE and UNIPORT on the effectiveness of the context, input, process and product of learner-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities

Table 4: One-Way Analysis analysis on effectiveness of context, input, process, and product of learner-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-cal	F-crit	Sig.	Remark
Between Groups	.575	2	.288	.996	3.23	.379	N.S
Within Groups	10.681	37	.289				
Total	11.256	39					

Research Data Output, 2021

Table 4 presents the One-Way ANOVA analysis on the effectiveness of context, input, process, and product of learner-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities. The analysis on showed that the f -cal (0.996) is less than the f -crit (3.23) at 0.05 level of significance, 2 degrees of freedom in the numerator and 37 degrees of freedom in the denominator. Furthermore, p -value obtained was 0.379 which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female psychology lecturers on the effectiveness of context, input, process, and product of learner-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities.

Discussion of findings

Table 1 presents the mean responses of lecturers on how effective the context, input, process and product of teacher-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses. Findings of the study revealed that teacher-centered instruction is effective in teachers' sole leadership/control of classroom management, limits students' activities in disrupting attention to the teacher, encouraging students' compliance to classroom rules over initiative, teachers' exert of discipline on students in the classroom, encouraging passive learners, boosting teachers' confident and comfort in instructional delivery among others. This finding agrees with Garret (2008), who noted in teacher-centered classrooms, control is of primary importance and "authority is transmitted hierarchically". Freiberg (1999) argues that the critics of teacher-centeredness argue that in these classrooms, compliance is valued over initiative and passive learners' over-active learners.

Table 2 presents the mean responses of lecturers on how effective the context, input, process and product of learner-centered methods for instructional delivery of psychological courses in Rivers State Universities. Findings of the study indicated that learner-centred instruction is effective in Shared leadership of teachers and students, guiding students to understanding, sharing classroom responsibilities and participation in learning activities, creates collaborative learning environment where knowledge is constructed by both teacher and

learner, students are expected to strive to make sense of what they are learning, aids construction of shared understanding, leads to learning by discovery and guidance, encouraging learners' initiatives amongst others. This finding corroborates with Garret (2008), Ubulom and Ogwunte (2017) who stated that student-centered approach focuses on meaning making, inquiry and authentic activity. He further stated that instructional goal in student-centred classrooms, based on constructivist principles of learning, is to create a learning environment where knowledge is constructed by the teacher and students rather than transmitted directly by the teacher.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that teacher-centered teaching methods and learner-centered teaching method are effective in their own ways for the teaching of psychological courses. However, the aim of teaching psychology courses in tertiary institution is to develop the intuitive ability in the learner which makes the course learner-centred. The learner centred approach according to the study, was found to be effective in sharing classroom responsibilities and participation in learning activities, encouraging learners' initiatives, creates balance between teachers' need and learners' need, aids construction of shared understanding and creates collaborative learning environment where knowledge is constructed by both teacher and learner. The strength of learner centred teaching method appears to be more needed in the teaching of psychological courses so as to achieve the aim of the course.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that;

1. Psychology lecturers should adopt areas of effectiveness in teacher-centred teaching method, so as to complement their various teaching methods used in conveying instructions to their learners.
2. Psychology lecturers should be trained on how best to utilize learner-centred teaching methods. This will enhance their effectiveness in achieving instructional goals and objectives.

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